

ROLE OF SAMANA VAYU IN AMLAPITTA: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE***¹Dr. Shital Subhashrao Magre, ²Dr. Rina Popatrao Deshmukh**

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ABSTRACT

Amlapitta is one of the most common disorders of the Annava Srotas characterized by symptoms such as Avipaka (indigestion), Tikta-Amla Udgara (sour and bitter eructation), Hrit-Kantha Daha (burning sensation in the chest and throat), Utklesha (nausea), and Chardi (vomiting). Although Amlapitta is primarily considered a Pitta-dominant disorder, the role of Vata, particularly Samana Vayu, is crucial in its pathogenesis. Samana Vayu governs digestion, assimilation, and regulation of Agni within the gastrointestinal tract. Any derangement of Samana Vayu leads to impairment of Agni, resulting in abnormal digestion and subsequent vitiation of Pachaka Pitta. This article explores the physiological functions of Samana Vayu and its contribution to the development and progression of Amlapitta.

KEYWORDS: Amlapitta, Annava Srotas, Avipaka,

Utklesha, Chardi, Pachaka.

INTRODUCTION

Amlapitta is described in Ayurvedic literature as a condition arising from the vitiation of Pitta due to improper dietary and lifestyle habits. Excessive consumption of sour, spicy, oily, fermented, and incompatible foods, along with psychological stress and irregular eating patterns, contributes to the development of the disease.

The pathogenesis of Amlapitta cannot be understood solely through the involvement of Pitta. The normal functioning of digestion depends on the harmonious interaction between Agni, Pachaka Pitta, Kledaka Kapha, and Samana Vayu. Among these factors, Samana Vayu plays a central regulatory role in maintaining digestive homeostasis. Concept of Saman Vayu.

Saman Vayu is one of the five subdivisions of Vata Dosha. It is situated in the region of Grahani and resides close to Jatharagni.

Functions of Saman Vayu

- Kindling and regulating digestive fire (Agni).
- Assisting digestion of ingested food.
- Facilitating separation of Sara (nutritive portion) and Kitta (waste products).
- Supporting absorption and assimilation of nutrients.
- Coordinating gastrointestinal motility.
- Maintaining equilibrium among digestive Doshas.

Through these actions, Saman Vayu acts as a bridge between Vata and Pitta in the digestive process.

Relationship Between Samana Vayu and Agni

Agni is the principal factor responsible for digestion and metabolism. Samana Vayu supports Agni by.

Bringing food into contact with digestive fire.

Disturbance of Samana Vayu results in Agnimandya (impaired digestive fire) or Vishama Agni (irregular digestive fire), creating favorable conditions for the development of Amlapitta.

Nidana of Amlapitta and Its Effect on Saman Vayu

The causative factors of Amlapitta include

Excessive consumption of spicy, sour, salty, fermented, and oily foods.

Irregular dietary habits. Overeating and eating before previous food is digested.

Excessive stress, anxiety, and emotional disturbances.

Daytime sleep and sedentary lifestyle.

These factors initially impair Agni and subsequently disturb the digestive function of Saman vayu resulting in Formation of Ama. Also, disturbance in its function results in excessive

stimulation of Pachak Pitta and improper coordination of Saman Vayu function with Apan and Pran vayu leading to upward movement of aggravated Pitta, causing symptoms such as Nausea, vomiting, and sour bleaching which are hallmarks of Amlapitta.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study material was collected from the following sources.

Classical Ayurvedic texts:

Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, Madhava Nidana, Bhavaprakasha

Published review articles, original research papers, and dissertations related to Samana Vayu, Agni, Grahani, and Amlapitta.

Relevant references pertaining to Samana Vayu, its Sthana (site), Karma (functions), and its relationship with Agni were identified and compiled from Ayurvedic classics.

Classical descriptions of Amlapitta, including Nidana (etiological factors), Purvarupa, Rupa, Samprapti, and Chikitsa, were reviewed.

Literature searches were performed using keywords such as “Samana Vayu,” “Amlapitta,” “Agni,” “Pachaka Pitta,” “Grahani,” and “Ayurvedic gastrointestinal disorders.”

The collected data were critically analyzed to understand the involvement of Samana Vayu in digestion, regulation of Agni, movement of Anna, and the pathogenesis of Amlapitta.

Correlations between the physiological functions of Samana Vayu and manifestations of Amlapitta were established based on textual evidence and contemporary scientific understanding of gastrointestinal physiology.

The reviewed information was synthesized and presented systematically to elucidate the Ayurvedic perspective on the role of Samana Vayu in Amlapitta.

CONCLUSION

Samana Vayu plays a vital role in maintaining proper digestion and balancing Agni. Its dysfunction contributes significantly to the pathogenesis of Amlapitta, while restoring its normal function helps in effective management and prevention of the disease.

REFERENCE

1. Ashtanga Hridaya

Author: Vagbhata

Reference: Sutrasthana 12/8–10

Edition: Kaviraj Atrideva Gupta & Yadunandana Upadhyaya, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan.

2. Charaka Samhita

Author: Charaka

Reference: Chikitsasthana 15 (Grahani Chikitsa)

Edition: Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan.

3. Madhava Nidana (Amlapitta Nidana)

Author: Madhavakara

Reference: Chapter 51 – Amlapitta Nidana

Although Samana Vayu is not described separately in detail, the pathogenesis of Amlapitta includes derangement of digestive mechanisms centered in Amashaya, where Samana Vayu acts along with Pachaka Pitta and Kledaka Kapha.

Edition: Madhava Nidana with Madhukosha Commentary by Vijayarakshita and Shrikanthadatta

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